

ENHANCING EARTHQUAKE EARLY WARNING ACCURACY: MACHINE LEARNING APPROACHES FOR RAPID SOURCE- LOCATION ESTIMATION

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ABSTRACT

We develop a random forest (RF) model for rapid earthquake location with an aim to assist earthquake early warning (EEW) systems in fast decision making. This system exploits P-wave arrival times at the first five stations recording an earthquake and computes their respective arrival time differences relative to a reference station (i.e., the first recording station). These differential P-wave arrival times and station locations are classified in the RF model to estimate the epicentral location. We train and test the proposed algorithm with an earthquake catalog from Japan. The RF model predicts the earthquake locations with a high accuracy, achieving a Mean Absolute Error (MAE) of 2.88 km. As importantly, the proposed RF model can learn from a limited amount of data (i.e., 10% of the dataset) and much fewer (i.e., three) recording stations and still achieve satisfactory results (MAE < 5 km). The algorithm is accurate, generalizable, and rapidly responding, thereby offering a powerful new tool for fast and reliable source-location prediction in EEW.

1. INTRODUCTION

EARTHQUAKE hypocenter localization is essential in the field of seismology and plays a critical role in a variety of seismological applications such as tomography, source characterization, and hazard assessment. This underscores the importance of developing robust earthquake monitoring systems for accurately determining the event origin times and hypocenter locations. In addition, the rapid and reliable characterization of ongoing earthquakes is a crucial, yet challenging, task for developing seismic hazard mitigation tools like earthquake early warning (EEW) systems [1]. While classical methods have been widely adopted to design EEW systems, challenges remain to pinpoint hypocenter locations in real-time largely due to limited information in the early stage of earthquakes. Among various key aspects of EEW, timeliness is a crucial consideration and additional efforts are required to further improve the hypocenter location estimates with minimum data from 1) the first few seconds after the P-wave arrival and 2) the first few seismograph stations that are triggered by the ground shaking.

The localization problem can be resolved using a sequence of detected waves (arrival times) and locations of seismograph stations that are triggered by ground shaking. Among various network architectures, the recurrent neural network (RNN) is capable of precisely extracting information from a sequence of input data, which is ideal for handling a group of seismic stations that are triggered sequentially following the propagation paths of seismic waves. This method has been investigated to improve the performance of real-time earthquake detection [2] and classification of source characteristics. Other machine learning based strategies have also been proposed for earthquake monitoring. Comparisons between traditional machine learning methods, including the nearest neighbor, decision tree, and the support vector machine, have also been made for the earthquake detection problem [3]. However, a common issue in the aforementioned machine learning based frameworks is that the selection of input features often requires expert knowledge, which may affect the accuracy of these methods. Convolution neural networks-based clustering methods have been used to regionalize earthquake epicenters [4] or predict their precise hypocenter locations [5]. In the latter case, three-component waveforms from multiple stations are exploited to train the model for swarm event localization.

In this study, we propose a RF-based method to locate earthquakes using the differential P-wave arrival times and station locations (Figure 1). The proposed algorithm only relies on P wave arrival

times detected at the first few stations. Its prompt response to earthquake first arrivals is critical for rapidly disseminating EEW alerts. Our strategy implicitly considers the influence of the velocity structures by incorporating the source-station locations into the RF model. We evaluate the proposed algorithm using an extensive seismic catalog from Japan. Our test results show that the RF model is capable of determining the locations of earthquakes accurately with minimal information, which sheds new light on developing efficient machine learning.

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

“Myshake: A smartphone seismic network for earthquake early warning and beyond,”

Large magnitude earthquakes in urban environments continue to kill and injure tens to hundreds of thousands of people, inflicting lasting societal and economic disasters. Earthquake early warning (EEW) provides seconds to minutes of warning, allowing people to move to safe zones and automated slowdown and shutdown of transit and other machinery. The handful of EEW systems operating around the world use traditional seismic and geodetic networks that exist only in a few nations. Smartphones are much more prevalent than traditional networks and contain accelerometers that can also be used to detect earthquakes. We report on the development of a new type of seismic system, MyShake, that harnesses personal/private smartphone sensors to collect data and analyze earthquakes. We show that smartphones can record

magnitude 5 earthquakes at distances of 10 km or less and develop an on-phone detection capability to separate earthquakes from other everyday shakes. Our proof-of-concept system then collects earthquake data at a central site where a network detection algorithm confirms that an earthquake is under way and estimates the location and magnitude in real time. This information can then be used to issue an alert of forthcoming ground shaking. MyShake could be used to enhance EEW in regions with traditional networks and could provide the only EEW capability in regions without. In addition, the seismic waveforms recorded could be used to deliver rapid microseism maps, study impacts on buildings, and possibly image shallow earth structure and earthquake rupture kinematics.

“Intelligent real-time earthquake detection by recurrent neural networks,”

Taiwan that is located at the junction of the Eurasian Plate and the Philippine Sea Plate is one of the most active seismic zones in the world. Devastating earthquakes have occurred around the island and have caused severe damages from time to time. To avoid the severe loss, earthquake early warning (EEW) is of great importance, and one of the most critical issues of EEW is fast and reliable detection for the presence of earthquakes. Traditional methods for earthquake detection usually use criterion-based algorithms to detect the onset of the earthquake waves. Currently, the thresholds for those criteria are usually decided empirically and may result in excessive false alarms. Obviously, false alarms can cause

undue panics and diminish the credibility of the system. In this article, the recurrent neural network (RNN) models are adopted to develop a real-time EEW system. The developed system is designed to identify the occurrence of an earthquake event, and the duration of the P-wave and the S-wave. It was trained and tested using the seismograms recorded in Taiwan from 2016 to 2017. From the simulation results, the proposed scheme outperforms the traditional criterion-based schemes in terms of detection accuracy and processing time.

“Learn to detect: Improving the accuracy of earthquake detection,”

Earthquake early warning system uses high-speed computer network to transmit earthquake information to population center ahead of the arrival of destructive earthquake waves. This short (10 s of seconds) lead time will allow emergency responses such as turning off gas pipeline valves to be activated to mitigate potential disaster and casualties. However, the excessive false alarm rate of such a system imposes heavy cost in terms of loss of services, undue panics, and diminishing credibility of such a warning system. At the current, the decision algorithm to issue an early warning of the onset of an earthquake is often based on empirically chosen features and heuristically set thresholds and suffers from excessive false alarm rate. In this paper, we experimented with three advanced machine learning algorithms, namely, K-nearest neighbor (KNN), classification tree, and support vector machine (SVM) and compared their performance against a traditional criterion-based method. Using the seismic data collected by an experimental

strong motion detection network in Taiwan for these experiments, we observed that the machine learning algorithms exhibit higher detection accuracy with much reduced false alarm rate.

3. EXISTING SYSTEM

Earthquake early warning (EEW) systems are required to report earthquake locations and magnitudes as quickly as possible before the damaging S wave arrival to mitigate seismic hazards. Deep learning techniques provide potential for extracting earthquake source information from full seismic waveforms instead of seismic phase picks.

We developed a novel deep learning EEW system that utilizes fully convolutional networks to simultaneously detect earthquakes and estimate their source parameters from continuous seismic waveform streams. The system determines earthquake location and magnitude as soon as very few stations receive earthquake signals and evolutionarily improves the solutions by receiving continuous data. We apply the system to the 2016 M 6.0 Central Apennines, Italy Earthquake and its first-week aftershocks. Earthquake locations and magnitudes can be reliably determined as early as 4 s after the earliest P phase, with mean error ranges of 8.5–4.7 km and 0.33–0.27, respectively.

Disadvantages

- An existing system method is not investigated to improve the performance of real-time earthquake

detection and classification of source characteristics.

- Convolution neural networks-based clustering methods have not been used to regionalize earthquake epicenters or predict their precise hypocenter locations.

4. PROPOSED SYSTEM

The system proposes a RF-based method to locate earthquakes using the differential P-wave arrival times and station locations (Figure 1). The proposed algorithm only relies on Pwave arrival times detected at the first few stations. Its prompt response to earthquake first arrivals is critical for rapidly disseminating EEW alerts. Our strategy implicitly considers the influence of the velocity structures by incorporating the source-station locations into the RF model.

The proposed system evaluates the proposed algorithm using an extensive seismic catalog from Japan. Our test results show that the RF model is capable of determining the locations of earthquakes accurately with minimal information, which sheds new light on developing efficient machine learning.

Advantages

- The number of stations is a critical factor that determines the data availability and prediction accuracy. The proposed RF model takes the arrival times of P waves recorded at multiple stations as the input, hence a more stringent requirement of simultaneous recording at an increased number of stations lowers the availability of qualified events.

- The localization problem can be resolved using a sequence of detected waves (arrival times) and locations of seismograph stations that are triggered by ground shaking. Among various network architectures, the recurrent neural network (RNN) is capable of precisely extracting information from a sequence of input data, which is ideal for handling a group of seismic stations that are triggered sequentially following the propagation paths of seismic waves.

5. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

6. IMPLEMENTATION

Modules

Service Provider

In this module, the Service Provider has to login by using valid user name and password. After login successful he can do some operations such as Login, Train & Test Data Sets, View Trained and Tested Accuracy in Bar Chart, View Trained and Tested Accuracy Results, View Prediction Of Earthquake Early Type Warning, View Earthquake Early Warning Type Ratio, Download Predicted Data Sets, View Earthquake Early Warning Type Ratio Results, View All Remote Users.

View Prediction Of Earthquake Early Type Warning, View Earthquake Early Warning Type Ratio, Download Predicted Data Sets, View Earthquake Early Warning Type Ratio Results, View All Remote Users.

View and Authorize Users

In this module, the admin can view the list of users who all registered. In this, the admin can view the user’s details such as, user name, email, address and admin authorizes the users.

Remote User

In this module, there are n numbers of users are present. User should register before doing any operations. Once user registers, their details will be stored to the database. After registration successful, he has to login by using authorized user name and password. Once Login is successful user will do some operations like REGISTER AND LOGIN, REDICT EARTHQUAKEEARLY WARNING TYPE, VIEW YOUR PROFILE.

7.CONCLUSION AND FUTURE ENHANCEMENT

We use the P-wave arrival time differences and the location of the seismic stations to locate the earthquake in a real-time way. Random forest (RF) has been proposed to perform this regression problem, where the difference latitude and longitude between the earthquake and the seismic stations are considered as the RF output. The Japanese seismic area is used as a case of study, which demonstrates very successful performance and indicates its immediate

applicability. We extract all the events having at least five P-wave arrival times from nearby seismic stations. Then, we split the extracted events into training and testing datasets to construct a machine learning model. In addition, the proposed method has the ability to use only three seismic stations and 10% of the available dataset for training, still with encouraging performance, indicating the flexibility of the proposed algorithm in real-time earthquake monitoring in more challenging areas. Despite the sparse distribution of many networks around the world, which makes the random forest method difficult to train an effective model, one can use numerous synthetic datasets to compensate for the shortage of ray paths in a target area due to insufficient catalog and station distribution.

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